

**International Journal of Cultural Studies
and Social Sciences**

ISSN : 2347 - 4777

CERTIFICATE OF PUBLICATION

This is to certify that the article entitled

**QUANTUM FLUCTUATIONS, THE BIG BANG, AND THE ENIGMA OF TIME: EXPLORING THE INTERPLAY OF
QUANTUM PHYSICS AND THE ORIGIN OF THE UNIVERSE**

Authored By

Mr. Shreyas R

JAIN (Deemed-to-be University) Bangalore India

Published in

International Journal of Cultural Studies and Social Sciences

ISSN 2347-4777 with IF=7.138

Vol-20, Issue-01, No.25, January - June: 2024

Double-Blind, Peer Reviewed, Refereed & Open Access, UGC CARE Listed Journal

